

POWERING A GREENER BENIN WITH RENEWABLE ENERGY BY 2050

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Executive Summary

Benin, like many Sub-Saharan African countries, faces persistent challenges in ensuring universal electricity access and advancing its energy transition despite ongoing projects and commitments under its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). As of 2023, national electricity access stands at 57.0%, with 70.3% coverage in urban areas and only 43.7% in rural areas (World Bank Group, 2023). The energy sector accounts for 63.62% of the country's greenhouse gas emissions, excluding the land use sector, highlighting its key role in climate mitigation efforts.

This study uses the OSeMOSYS modeling framework to develop and analyze long-term energy planning scenarios for Benin through 2050. It compares two policy scenarios to a business-as-usual baseline. Scenario 1 aims to reduce energy-related CO₂ emissions by 50% by 2050 through a cleaner, more diverse energy mix. Scenario 2 focuses on increasing renewable energy installed capacity by at least 25% by 2050.

Although Scenario 1 requires slightly higher investment, only 0.06% more than Scenario 2, they result in comparable emissions reductions of around 70 million tons of CO₂. Future research should include updated data, sector-specific energy use analyses, and incorporate spatial modeling for improved regional planning.

1. Introduction

Energy transition is a strategic priority in Benin's National Renewable Energy Development Policy (PONADER) and its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), which targets a 20.15% reduction in cumulative greenhouse gas emissions over the 2021–2030 period.

Among the 21 mitigation measures outlined in the NDC's emission projections for 2019–2030, 12 measures encompass 20 actions specifically within the energy sector. However, despite these commitments and initiatives, the national electricity production remains limited, with only 3.3% generated from solar photovoltaic (PV) sources, compared to 73.1% from natural gas and 23.6% from oil.

In this context, three primary research questions warrant scientific investigation:

- ✓ What is Benin's energy expansion capacity by 2050?
- ✓ How could Benin achieve better decarbonization of its electricity generation, cutting associated emissions by half by 2050?
- ✓ What is the most cost-effective renewable energy mix that can be implemented to meet energy demand in an environmentally sustainable manner by 2050?

2. Methodology

This study employs a linear optimization approach using OSeMOSYS to construct a long-term energy system model for Benin, with a planning horizon to 2050. The energy system is represented as a bottom-up techno-economic model, using linear programming to minimize total system cost, including capital, operation, maintenance, and fuel expenses, while satisfying energy demand and emissions constraints. Input data are drawn from multiple authoritative sources, including national reports (e.g., Benin's updated NDC, Benin Sustainable Development Report 2024.), international organizations such as the World Bank, IRENA, and the International Energy Agency, and academic literature. Additionally, data from the ECOWREX platform of ECOWAS/CEDEAO were employed for spatially resolved information on renewable resource potential, energy access, and infrastructure.

To this end, three scenarios were developed for comparative analysis.

- Baseline (BAU) Scenario: Projects future development based on historical trends and current government policies, assuming these continue through 2050.

- Scenario 1: Assumes a 50% reduction in CO₂ emissions from Benin's energy sector by 2050, achieved through a cleaner and more diversified energy mix.

- Scenario 2: Assumes at least a 25% increase in installed renewable energy capacity (solar, biogas, wind, etc.) by 2050, aligned with current government policy and NDC commitments.

Furthermore, taking into account Benin's current energy policy and infrastructure plans, natural gas-based electricity generation was retained in the projections through 2050, notably due to ongoing investments such as the Maria-Gléta natural gas plant.

3. Results

As illustrated in Figure 1, all three scenarios address growing electricity demand in distinct ways, with each scenario deploying a different mix of generation technologies tailored to projected demand trajectories.

Figure 1. Production by Technology By Mode

In addition, beyond their comparable energy production levels, 12,391 PJ and 12,361 PJ respectively, scenario 1 and scenario 2 rely primarily on solar energy for electricity generation, followed by wind power and Diesel Offgrid. This results in respective accumulated new capacities of 50.0534 GW and 48.199 GW by the year 2050.

Figure 2. Accumulated New Capacity

Regarding costs, both Scenarios 1 and 2 exhibit higher annualized investment costs compared to the baseline scenario, amounting to USD 800.295 million and USD 799.779 million, respectively, versus USD 797.303 million for the baseline, as shown in Figure 3. This superiority could be explained by the continued investment and the acquisition of new renewable power plants and a storage system in both scenarios.

Figure 3. Annualized Investment cost

In terms of environmental feasibility, the results indicate that both scenarios are environmentally efficient. Each leads to reductions in CO₂ emissions compared to the baseline scenario. In other words, only emissions from natural gas, fuel oil, and diesel power plants persist, though at significantly reduced levels relative to the baseline. Specifically, total CO₂ emissions amount to 22.3438 million tonnes and 22.344 million tonnes for Scenarios 1 and 2, respectively, compared to 41.5872 million tonnes under the baseline scenario in 2050 if the status quo were maintained. This outcome can be attributed to the considerable proportion of renewable energy in Scenarios 1 and 2.

F4. Annual Technology Emission

4. Discussion

The OSeMOSYS results highlight key differences and similarities across the three energy scenarios. Scenarios 1 and 2 address rising electricity demand through greater integration of renewable technologies. Both achieve comparable energy outputs, 12,391 PJ and 12,361 PJ respectively, demonstrating less than 0.3% variation in system production.

Solar power is the dominant energy source in both scenarios, followed by wind and off-grid diesel. Notably, wind power deployment begins earlier in Scenario 2 in 2030 compared to Scenario 1 in 2039, contributing to a smoother transition. Scenario 2 also features improved energy storage capacity, enhancing system flexibility.

This leads to accumulated new capacities of 50.05 GW for Scenario 1 and 48.20 GW for Scenario 2 by 2050, underscoring the strong role of renewables.

Economically, Scenarios 1 and 2 show slightly higher annualized investment costs, USD 800.30 million and USD 799.78 million, compared to USD 797.30 million for the baseline (Figure 3). This increase remains below 0.4%, suggesting that low-carbon development is achievable at minimal additional cost.

Environmentally, both scenarios are significantly more efficient. CO₂ emissions drop to 22.34 million tonnes in both cases, compared to 41.59 million tonnes under the baseline by 2050, a reduction of approximately 46%. These improvements stem from reduced fossil fuel use, especially fuel oil and diesel.

Overall, Scenarios 1 and 2 provide cost-effective and sustainable pathways for long-term electricity planning.

5. Conclusion

This analysis employing the OSeMOSYS model has demonstrated that Scenarios 1 and 2 offer technically feasible and economically viable pathways to meet projected electricity demand by 2050. Both scenarios prioritize the deployment of solar and wind energy, with Scenario 2 showing an earlier integration of wind power from 2030 and enhanced energy storage capacity, contributing to greater system flexibility. Despite marginally higher annualized investment costs, less than 0.4 percent above the baseline, these scenarios achieve substantial environmental benefits, reducing CO₂ emissions by approximately 46 percent relative to the status quo.

Key lessons highlight the critical importance of accelerating renewable energy adoption and scaling storage infrastructure to ensure grid reliability and resilience. The reduction in reliance on fossil fuels, particularly fuel oil and diesel, is essential to achieving national and international climate commitments.

To translate these modeling insights into practical action, an initiative to establish the first Living Lab for energy modeling and renewable energy co-creation is underway, involving multiple stakeholders. We are confident that this collaborative program will yield tangible outcomes that support the sustainable energy transition.

It is therefore recommended that policymakers and stakeholders prioritize policies that facilitate early renewable integration and invest in advanced storage technologies. Further studies should focus on detailed cost-benefit analyses of storage solutions and demand-side management strategies to optimize the energy transition. These measures will strengthen the country's sustainable development trajectory while ensuring energy security.

References

African Union Energy (2022). Africa Energy Balance & Indicators 2022

Benin Government (2020). National renewable energy development policy (Politique Nationale de Développement des Energies Renouvelables (PONADER))

Chiffres clés 2021 Bilans énergétiques et indicateurs 2016 à 2020)

Department of Energy Resources, (2021). Key statistics 2021, energy balances and indicators 2016 to 2020 (Direction Générale des Ressources Énergétiques, (2021).

ECOWREX. (2025). ECOWAS Observatory for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency. Retrieved from <https://www.ecowrex.org>

International Energy Agency. (2025). Benin: Electricity. Retrieved July 30, 2025, from <https://www.iea.org/countries/benin/electricity>

IRENA (2025), Renewable capacity statistics 2025, International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi

NDC Partnership (2021). Benin First NDC (Updated submission)

OSCI - CCI Bénin (2023). Summary: Industry Key Data (Synthèse Chiffres Clés Industrie Mars 2023)

OSCI-CCI Benin. (2025). Key Figures on Renewable Energy. April 2025 (Chiffres clés sur les énergies renouvelables, (OSCI-CCI Bénin, Avril 2025))

Sustainable Development Report for Benin 2024. (Government of Benin, 2024)

Strategizing towards sustainable energy planning: Modeling the mix of future generation technologies for 2050 in Benin, Romain Akpahou, Flavio Odoi-Yorke, Lena D. Mensah, David A Quansha, Francis Kemausuor (2024)

U.S. Energy Information Administration. (2025). Benin – International energy data and analysis. Retrieved July 30, 2025, from <https://www.eia.gov/international/overview/country/BEN>

World Bank. (2025). Access to electricity (% of population) [Data set]. Retrieved July 30, 2025, from <https://donnees.banquemondiale.org/indicateur/EG.ELC.ACCS.ZS>

Appendices

Concept Note

This preliminary concept note presents the rationale and objectives of the proposed Living Lab on Energy Modeling and Renewable Energy in Benin. It is included for informational purposes only and reflects the current stage of co-creation with participating stakeholders. Click [here](#) for more information:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1WwjHm9jopIEIa9p6INpW6EuDbI9tKRhA?usp=drive_link